

2. Schematic diagram of the genetic crosses between *N. bakeri* (Nb) and *N. lugens* (NI), IRRRI, 1982.

hatchability. Hatchability was 11 and 21% in the direct and reciprocal interspecific crosses, while hatchability in conspecific crosses was 86 and 91%.

2. The genitalic characters of F₁ progenies of the interspecific crosses resembled those of their respective immediate female parent. When selfed to produce

F₂, and backcrossed, a similar genetic transmission mechanism was found. An exception was a backcross involving (F₁)Nb♀ x (P)NI♂, which failed to produce any offspring. The mechanisms for such maternal inheritance may involve:

- cytoplasmic inheritance, wherein the characters are determined or controlled by independent cytoplasmic genes;
- maternal effects, wherein the characters are controlled by nuclear genes, but behave through the effects produced in the maternal cytoplasm; or
- gynogenesis, wherein the sperm serves only to activate the egg and plays no further part in fertilization nor contributes to the genetic constitution of the embryo.

These observations indicate the existence of some pre- and post-mating barriers between *N. bakeri* and *N. lugens*. Their genetic incompatibility negates possibility of interspecific hybridization occurring in nature. □

Microvelia atrolineata Bergroth, a predaceous bug of *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål)

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Veliid bug *Microvelia atrolineata* was found for the first time in Karnataka during a survey for natural enemies of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* during 1982 wet season. The bugs were feeding on BPH nymphs.

Veliid adults and nymphs were found on the water surface around BPH-infested

rice hills. When BPH nymphs dropped onto the water, the veliid bugs paralyzed and fed upon them. As many as six veliid bugs (see figure) attacked a single BPH nymph. There were 10-12 veliid bugs/400 cm² when the crop was at milk stage. Bugs are active and run on the water surface. Population did not fluctuate at different water levels as long as the field remained saturated.

Because veliid bugs feed voraciously on first- and second-instar BPH nymphs, they may contribute to significant pest mortality. □

Veliid bugs attacking a BPH nymph.

Pest management and control NEMATODES

Root-knot nematode damage to rice in West Bengal, India

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Root-knot nematode damaged about 8 10 ha of aus (Mar-Jun) paddy in the drylands of Islampur and Balurghat subdivisions of West Dinajpur. Foliage yellowed, number of tillers and yield were reduced, and plants lost growth vigor.

Plant analysis showed 30 galls and 90 females with or without egg masses/10 g of rice roots. Varieties IET2233,

IET1444, and CNM25, grown on seed farms in Islampur and Chopra, were seriously damaged. The nematode also attacked standing crops in farmer fields in Balurghat and Tapan Block.

Nematodes were cultured on TN1. Measurements were:

10 females: length = 395-490 μm, width = 290-350 μm, stylet = 11 μm,

length/greatest width = 1.4.

5 males: length = 1,150-1,248 µm, stylet = 16.5 µm, length/greatest width = 150-175, spicule = 11.5 µm.

20 second-stage juveniles: length = 42040 µm, length/greatest width =

25-27, length/esophagus length = 3.44.0, length/tail length = 6.0-6.5, stylet = 11.5-12 µm.

Measurements and the perineal pattern of females indicated the species is *Meloidogyne graminicola* Golden and

Birchfield. The nematode is found in Orissa, Assam, and Tripura States of India; Bangladesh; Thailand; and Louisiana, United States. This is the first record of the nematode in West Bengal. □

Control of rice root nematode

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Rice root nematode *Hirschmaniella oryzae* is an important rice pest in India and other countries. Nematode populations are high in flooded, heavy alluvial soils.

Nursery and root-soak pesticide appli-

cations were tested for nematode control on IR20 at two locations in Tamil Nadu in 1980-81 (see table). Treatments were replicated thrice in 4-m² nursery beds and 2 × 1 m plots at 20 × 15 cm spacing.

Root samples were collected at monthly intervals until harvest by randomly uprooting one plant from each plot. Nematodes separated from the roots by the Baermann pan technique were counted.

Grain yield, plant height, root length, and root weight were recorded.

Nematode populations ranged from 18 to 270 per 5 g of root examined from different treatments (see table).

Application of carbofuran 3% G at 1 kg ai/ha in the nursery at sowing, followed by phenamiphos or carbosulfone 0.2% root soak, significantly reduced nematode populations and increased grain yield. □

Effect of pesticides on rice root nematode at 2 locations, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Nematicide		Aduthurai					Sirugamani				
Seedbed	Seedling root soak	Popu- lation (TV)	Plant ht (cm)	Roots		Grain yield (kg/2 m ²)	Popu- lation (crv)	Plant ht (cm)	Roots		Grain yield ² (kg/2 m ²)
				Length (cm)	Weight (g)				Length (cm)	Weight (g)	
Carbofuran 3% G 1 kg ai/ha	Carbosulfone 24 EC at 0.2% concn	6.35	94.0	30.0	27.3	0.67	7.57	77.7	32.3	28.0	0.75
Carbofuran 3% G 1 kg ai/ha	Phenamiphos 40 EC at 0.2% concn	7.17	94.3	30.3	19.0	0.71	5.70	82.3	36.7	30.0	0.78
Metham sodium 77.5 kg ai/ha	Dimethoate 30 EC at 0.2%	9.90	84.0	23.7	17.0	0.42	8.10	79.3	33.0	23.3	0.45
Metham sodium 77.5 kg ai/ha	-	10.20	89.7	27.7	25.3	0.41	9.87	78.3	32.0	21.7	0.47
Untreated check C. D.		11.63	81.7	31.3	20.0	0.41	13.20	70.7	28.7	22.0	0.39
		1.33	N.S.	4.0	3.7	0.061	1.33	6.0	4.57	N.S.	0.06

^aMeans for 3 replications. ^bTV = transformed values of $\sqrt{x+0.5}$ where 'x' stands for the nematode population.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of planting density and submergence level on weed density in rice fields

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Effect of planting density and submergence level on weed density was recorded at 70 sites in Nadia District, West Bengal, during the 1981 wet season. Sites were planted with medium-duration improved rice varieties.

1. Relationship between planting density and weed density.